

Analyzing COVID-19 on a Global Scale: Investigating its Worldwide Ramifications

Mustapha Abdulsalam^{1*}, Khadija Muntaqa Tijjani Usman², Amina Abdulkadir Nurudeen³, Fatima Yusuf Muhammad⁴

Department of Microbiology, School of Science and Information Technology, Skyline University Nigeria

Corresponding Author: Mustapha Abdulsalam abdulxsalam22@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: BatCoV RaTG13, SARS-CoV-2 genome, coronavirus, vaccination, PCR.

Received : 26, August

Revised : 18, September

Accepted: 25, October

©2023 Abdulsalam, Usman, Nurudeen, Muhammad: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

The most recent coronavirus information and updates, including the number of confirmed cases, deaths, and affected countries worldwide, are outlined in this study. There were approximately 700 million confirmed cases and 6 million deaths globally at the time of the study. To manage and prevent the virus from spreading, the World Health Organization (WHO) has established guidelines and recommendations for safety measures like vaccination, wearing face masks, avoiding social situations, maintaining proper hand hygiene, and restricting travel. The emergence of novel virus variants highlights the need for ongoing vigilance and adaptation in public health, and ongoing research has guided the development of effective vaccines and treatments.

INTRODUCTION

The extremely intense respiratory condition (SARS-CoV-2) sparked a global pandemic of coronavirus disease in 2019 (Singhal, 2020). Within the span of the pandemic, SARS-CoV-2 has mutated regularly, resulting in variants that are distinct from the original SARS-CoV-2 virus. Many SARS-CoV-2 variants have been discovered worldwide during the COVID-19 pandemic (Karim & Karim, 2021). The Coronavirus disease, which has proactively killed many thousands and infected millions, arose in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 (Singhal, 2020; Qiu et al., 2020). There were approximately 770 million confirmed cases and 6 million deaths have been reported globally as of 23rd September 2023. Coronavirus can be transmitted through contact with contaminated surfaces, but the primary vector is the respiratory tract (Dambha-Miller et al., 2023). A fever, cough, fatigue, shortness of breath, sore throat, body aches, and loss of taste and smell are all possible side effects of the condition. Coronavirus can, in extreme cases, result in pneumonia, severe respiratory distress, and death (Klein et al., 2021).

When evaluating coronavirus, imaging, testing with an emphasis on research, and clinical adverse effects are fully considered. For respiratory samples, real-time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) testing is the gold standard for diagnosis (Hernández- Huerta et al., 2021). The diagnosis and treatment of a condition can also be aided by chest X-rays and computed tomography (CT) imaging (Goudouris, 2021). There are currently no antiviral medicines for Coronavirus. The majority of treatment is supportive and emphasizes relieving symptoms, administering oxygen, and reducing the probability of complications like pneumonia and respiratory failure (Klein et al., 2021). As a preventative measure, vaccines against COVID-19 have been produced and are currently being distributed worldwide. To inhibit the virus from spreading, rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) and preventative measures like wearing a mask and getting vaccinated are vital (Qiu et al., 2020). Further study is essential to reveal effective treatments and gain a more profound comprehension of COVID-19. More efforts are required to alleviate the effects of COVID-19, which continues to pose a threat to public health (Karim & Karim, 2021).

Since the beginning of the outbreak, there has been a remarkable increase in both confirmed cases and mortality rates, especially in countries considered by high transmission rates and low vaccination coverage (Yang et al., 2020). The United States, India, Brazil, Russia, and the United Kingdom all have the highest number of confirmed cases (Nabi, 2020). Despite this, extensive vaccination campaigns and the implementation of control and countermeasures have resulted in a decrease in both new cases and mortality rates in many countries. Several countries have adopted the Delta strain of the influenza virus, which is more contagious and has the potential to cause more severe infection (Ao et al., 2021). This has led to an increase in cases and hospitalizations in areas with low vaccination rates. New viral strains, like the Omicron strain, are the theme of intensive research by public health officials (Araf et al., 2022).

Vaccination is necessary to avoid serious illness, hospitalization, and virus transmission. In terms of vaccination, many countries have made progress, with some achieving high vaccination rates. In any case, immune response movement and execution keep on being given in various pieces of the globe (Biswas et al., 2021). Health professionals continue to stress the importance of taking precautions like wearing a veil, separating from others, washing one's hands, and isolating or quarantining those who are infected or have been exposed to the infection (Nabi, 2020). Various countries have executed travel limitations and quarantine approaches to forestall the spread of sickness. COVID-19's situation is rapidly changing as a result of regular reports from public health organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO) and local health departments on new cases, deaths, and affected nations. To safeguard themselves and their communities, individuals must be aware of and implement recommended security measures (Güner et al., 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

In 2019, SARS-CoV-2 causes coronavirus disease. SARS-CoV-2 has a place with the group of encased, single-abandoned, positive-sense RNA infections known as the Coronaviridae (Hu et al., 2021). This group of infections includes four genera: Alpha, Beta, Gamma, and Delta are all coronaviruses (Khan et al., 2020). The virus that caused the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) outbreak in 2012 (MERS-CoV) and the SARS-CoV epidemic in 2002-2003 are both members of the genus Beta-coronavirus (Zhou et al., 2021). In Wuhan, China, in December 2019, the SARS-CoV-2 virus was found close to a seafood and live animal market. The virus was also being passed from one person to another, according to an investigation, which led to a rapid global pandemic (Güner et al., 2020). COVID-19 is primarily spread through infected people's respiratory tract. The symptoms of some respiratory illnesses, which range from mild to severe, can be fatal. The approximately 30,000 nucleotides and 27 proteins in the genome of SARS-CoV-2 enable it to be categorized according to its genetic characteristics (Schlick et al., 2021). There are four structural proteins in the virus: film (M), nucleocapsid (N), envelope (E), and spike (S). The pathogen's ability to enter cells is dependent on the S protein, which is the focus of numerous efforts to develop vaccines and drugs (Gordon et al., 2020). It is hypothesized that SARS-CoV-2 is zoonotic, and that implies that it started in a creature supply and was sent to people. Genetic evidence suggests that the virus may have originated in bats and evolved into an intermediate host, most likely a pangolin, before infecting humans (Guo et al., 2020). The virus's precise origin is unknown. This hypothesis is supported by the discovery of a bat coronavirus whose disposition links to that of SARS-CoV-2 at 96%. Effective vaccinations and treatments require knowledge of SARS-CoV-2 classification and origin. Recognizing the disease's origins will improve diagnostics, antivirals, and genetic makeup to prevent future zoonotic outbreaks (Salian et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The most recent coronavirus information and updates, including the number of confirmed cases, deaths, and affected countries worldwide, are outlined in this study. There were approximately 700 million confirmed cases and 6 million deaths globally at the time of the study. To manage and prevent the virus from spreading, the World Health Organization (WHO) has established guidelines and recommendations for safety measures like vaccination, wearing face masks, avoiding social situations, maintaining proper hand hygiene, and restricting travel. The emergence of novel virus variants highlights the need for ongoing vigilance and adaptation in public health, and ongoing research has guided the development of effective vaccines and treatments.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The virus: Origin and classification

The fact that bat coronavirus and SARS-CoV-2 share 96% of their genomic sequence (Guo et al., 2020). The virus's genome consists of approximately 30,000 nucleotides and 27 proteins. The S protein plays a basic part in the disease's ability to go after cells, and it is the target of different vaccinations and therapeutics at this point work is underway. Understanding the SARS-CoV-2 classification and origin is essential for the development of effective vaccines and treatments. Antiviral treatments and diagnostic devices can be guided by the infection's inherited structure, and information about its origins can help prevent future zoonotic outbreaks (Asselah et al., 2021). SARS-CoV-2, a brand-new coronavirus, most likely originated in bats. The infection is strongly associated with other bats, such as BatCoV RaTG13, and shares a common progenitor with SARS-CoV, which caused the SARS outbreak in 2003, according to the genomic analysis (Fernández, 2021). Recombination events have been found in the genome of SARS-CoV-2, indicating that the virus may have genetically interacted with other viruses. One review, for example, observed that the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2, which is fundamental for the infection to enter cells, is the same as the spike protein of a pangolin coronavirus, recommending that the two infections might have recombined (Raza et al., 2021). Another study also found that a portion of the SARS-CoV-2 genome is very similar to a snake-specific viral sequence; However, there is still some debate regarding this finding's validity (Jungreis et al., 2021). Even though recombination events are fairly common among coronaviruses, some researchers have speculated that SARS-CoV-2 may have recombined in a host other than bats, such as pangolins or humans, due to the virus's high rate of recombination (Cherian et al., 2021). However, further research is required to back up these hypotheses. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, appears to be a brand-new coronavirus that may have evolved through recombination with other viruses and probably originated in bats (Guo et al., 2020). More research is required to fully comprehend the development and origin of this virus.

Transmission

When an infected person speaks, coughs, or sneezes, respiratory droplets are the primary method by which the COVID-19-causing SARS-CoV-2 virus is spread. These droplets may enter the lungs if they land on an individual's mouth or nose (Singhal, 2020). The virus can also spread through direct contact with an infected person, such as through handshakes or by touching surfaces that have been contaminated with the virus and then touching one's mouth, eyes, or nose (Konatham et al., 2020). It's important to remember that even people who don't show symptoms can spread the virus. A person infected with the virus can spread the virus without showing any symptoms for two to fourteen days (Baud et al., 2020). Late examinations propose that the infection can likewise be communicated using airborne transmission, which involves more modest particles that can travel farther than respiratory drops and stay in the air for longer spans (Zhao et al., 2022). The scientific community conducts ongoing research and debate on this topic. Transmission through contaminated surfaces and from feces to mouth has also been proposed, but they are thought to be less common than respiratory transmission (Mehraeen et al., 2021). It is possible to slow the virus's spread by covering up, avoiding others, and occasionally cleaning up. Vaccines have been developed and are currently being distributed worldwide to assist in controlling the spread of COVID-19. Asymptomatic transmission alludes to the transmission of an illness by people who show no side effects of the sickness (Jones & Roy, 2021). On account of the coronavirus, it is accepted that SARS-CoV-2 transporters who don't display side effects can, in any case, communicate the infection. It is hard to gauge and evaluate how much asymptomatic transmission adds to the infection's general spread, which adds to the contention encompassing this subject. Several studies have found that asymptomatic people may be to blame for a significant number of Coronavirus cases, while others have found that most transmission occurs between people who are symptomatic (Sayampanathan et al., 2021). The possibility of pre-indicative transmission makes the situation even more complicated. Presymptomatic transmission occurs when individuals who will eventually experience symptoms but have not yet done so transmit the virus to others (Sayampanathan et al., 2021). As a result, people who were asymptomatic at the time of transmission may later experience symptoms. Despite the controversy, it is generally accepted that asymptomatic transmission can occur and that, regardless of whether a person displays symptoms, measures like wearing masks and maintaining social distancing can aid in preventing the virus's spread (Sayampanathan et al., 2021).

Risk factors

Since its development in December 2019, Coronavirus, brought about by the novel SARS-CoV-2, has quickly spread across the globe, influencing individuals of any age and medical issue (Hashim et al., 2020). Nonetheless, certain gatherings are more powerless to serious sickness and mortality brought about by Coronavirus. Age is a big risk factor, and people over 60 years of age are more likely to get sick because their immune systems change as they get

older (Verity et al., 2020). The risk of COVID-19-related severe illness and death is also increased by underlying medical conditions that weaken the immune system, such as diabetes, heart disease, chronic lung disease, and immunocompromising conditions (Hashim et al., 2020). Corpulence is a risk factor for severe Coronavirus disease, especially in younger adults who are more likely to have diabetes and heart disease as underlying medical conditions (Hutchins et al., 2020). Furthermore, the character is a gamble factor for serious sickness and demise from coronavirus, with specific ethnic gatherings, like Dark, Hispanic, and Local American populaces, being at a higher gamble. Social determinants of health, such as inaccessibility to healthcare, overcrowding, and higher rates of underlying health conditions, could be to blame for this. Jobs are likewise a critical gambling factor (Almeida-Pititto et al., 2020). Due to their jobs, healthcare workers, first responders, and essential workers are more likely to get COVID-19. These individuals might have restricted admittance to individual defensive hardware and are bound to come into contact with tainted individuals. COVID-19 transmission is also influenced by living conditions. Coronavirus transmission is more likely to occur in congested everyday settings like nursing homes, jails, and homeless shelters (Salien et al., 2021). These people might have less admittance to medical care and be bound to have fundamental medical issues. COVID-19 risk increases with travel history. Travelers are more likely to spread COVID-19 in regions where it is prevalent. Social interactions, on the other hand, contribute to the spread of COVID-19. Attending large gatherings without a mask and practicing physical separation are social behaviors that increase the risk of COVID-19 transmission. Instances of Coronavirus that have been accounted for demonstrate that people with at least one of these gamble factors are bound to get a serious disease and die from the infection (Ciotti et al., 2020). Masks, physical separation, and frequent hand washing are all necessary safety measures for those most at risk. Additionally, getting vaccinated against COVID-19 significantly lowers the risk of severe illness and death (Klein et al., 2021; Ciotti et al., 2020).

Pathogenesis and Immune Response

The virus enters the cells by interacting with the host cell receptor for angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) through the viral spike (S) protein. ACE is found in the kidneys, the cardiovascular system, the gastrointestinal tract, and the respiratory epithelium (Bourgonje et al., 2020). The infection imitates and creates extra popular particles once it enters the host cells, accordingly spreading all through the body. Vulnerability encompasses coronavirus' pathogenesis, yet it is remembered to include a dysregulated safe reaction and cytokine storm that causes organ and tissue harm (Rothan & Byrareddy, 2020). The naturally resistant framework is activated following SARS-CoV-2 infection, resulting in the production of proinflammatory cytokines like IL-6, TNF- α , and type I interferons. These cytokines bring immune cells like neutrophils and macrophages to the infection site, where they kill the virus and infected cells (Ouassou et al., 2020). However, evidence suggests that severe cases of Coronavirus are associated with a cytokine storm

and a dysregulated immune response, which may result in damage to healthy organs and tissues. This immune response is characterized by elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-6, IL-1, and TNF- α , which cause systemic inflammation and multi-organ failure. According to research, people with severe COVID-19 also have lower levels of Type I interferons, which are necessary for controlling viral replication (Lu et al., 2021). The versatile safe reaction also plays a crucial role in controlling SARS-CoV-2 transmission (Rokni et al., 2020). According to research, individuals with severe COVID-19 may exhibit impaired T-cell responses, which are essential for controlling viral infections. Non-neutralizing antibodies also appear to promote viral entry and replication in the phenomenon known as antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE). COVID-19's pathogenesis is a complicated process that involves cytokine storms and dysregulated immune responses, so ADE may also play a role in it, as it has in other coronaviruses like SARS-CoV and Middle East respiratory syndrome-CoV (Yager, 2020). Long-term immunity requires the adaptive immune response while controlling viral replication requires the innate immune response. Disruption of these immune responses can result in severe illness or death by causing damage to healthy tissues and organs (Khoury et al., 2021).

Clinical manifestation

Pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) are the most common clinical manifestations of 2019-nCoV infection. The length of the incubating time frame goes from 2 to 14 days, with a middle of 5 to 6 days. Patients tainted with 2019-nCoV oftentimes report fever, hack, weariness, myalgia, and dyspnea. Some of the rarer symptoms include a sore throat, diarrhea, vomiting, anosmia (loss of smell), and ageusia (loss of taste). The infection can quickly progress to ARDS, septic shock, and organ failure in severe cases (Archer et al., 2020). Severe illness and complications are more likely to occur in immunocompromised patients as well as those with preexisting conditions like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory disease, and cancer (Ko et al., 2021).

Clinical advents of SARS-CoV disease are like those of 2019-nCoV contamination. Fever, cough, dyspnea, and myalgia are among the SARS-CoV infection symptoms that are most frequently mentioned. SARS-CoV disease can quickly advance to ARDS, septic shock, and different organ dissatisfaction, like 2019-nCoV transmission (Giannis et al., 2020). Serious illness and complications are also more likely to occur in elderly, immunocompromised, or pre-existing medical conditions patients. Fever, congestion, dyspnea, and myalgia are the symptoms of 2019-nCoV infections are most common. The clinical signs and symptoms of SARS-CoV infections are comparable. The two contaminations can quickly advance to extreme ailments and difficulties, especially in older patients and those with other ailments (Yang et al., 2020).

Laboratory findings

Among other laboratory findings, COVID-19 is linked to abnormalities in routine blood tests, chest imaging, and viral detection methods. Leukopenia, or a low white blood cell count, lymphopenia, or a low lymphocyte count, and thrombocytopenia, or a low platelet count, may be found in severe disease patients during routine blood tests. What's more, raised degrees of provocative cytokines like C-responsive protein (CRP), development putrefactive variable alpha (TNF- α), and interleukin-6 (IL-6) are now and again seen in serious cases (Udomsinprasert et al., 2021). The opposite record polymerase chain response (RT-PCR) testing of respiratory samples like sputum, nasal swabs, and throat swabs is the highest quality level for Coronavirus analysis. Two extra demonstrative techniques are antigen discovery measures and serological testing for the location of infection-explicit antibodies (Santa Cruz et al., 2021). Patients with severe disease may experience an increase in the liver enzymes alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and creatine kinase (CK). Coagulation irregularities in extreme cases incorporate raised D-dimer levels and an extended prothrombin time (PT). Individual laboratory results can be very different from one another and are not always accurate indicators of the severity or prognosis of a disease (Wang et al., 2020). For the treatment of COVID-19 patients, clinical assessments and careful observation of the patient's symptoms and vital signs are essential (Xu et al., 2020).

Radiology findings

In the finding and checking of Coronavirus, the utilization of radiologic imaging procedures like chest X-beams and registered tomography (CT) filters has expanded essentially. In Coronavirus patients, two-sided, multifocal ground-glass opacities (GGOs) and unions are frequent radiologic findings, primarily in the lung periphery and sub-pleural regions (Ng et al., 2020).

On CT scans, ground-glass opacities permit some X-rays to penetrate the lung tissue. In consolidations, alveolar infill increases attenuation and eliminates aeration. Coronavirus pathology, which consists of incendiary cell penetration and diffuse alveolar damage, is supported by these radiological findings (Paterson et al., 2020). In addition to GGOs and unions, patients with the coronavirus may also have insanity-clearing patterns, air bronchograms, and knobs as additional radiologic findings (Sultan & Sehgal, 2020). GGOs displaying interlobular and intralobular septal thickness indicate psychosis, whereas air bronchograms depict air-filled bronchi in a hazy lung tract. Even though they are less common than GGOs and solidifications, knobs may also be accessible. Radiologic imaging is useful for monitoring the progression of the disease and determining the efficacy of a treatment, in addition to assisting in the diagnosis of COVID-19. Follow-up CT outputs can help with settling on clinical choices by uncovering whether lung sores have improved or declined (Sultan & Sehgal, 2020). However, it is essential to keep in mind that radiologic findings cannot be used to diagnose COVID-19 on their own due to the possibility that they overlap with other respiratory infections or conditions that are not infectious (Ng et al., 2020). However, because it provides crucial

information about the disease's severity and response to treatment, radiologic imaging is a useful tool for managing COVID-19.

Treatment

The treatment for COVID-19 is still being developed as researchers continue to investigate the virus and its effects on the human body. For the treatment of COVID-19, no specific antiviral medications are currently approved (Stasi et al., 2020). Instead, the treatment plan focuses on controlling symptoms and avoiding problems. One of the most common treatments for COVID-19 is supportive care. This incorporates the treatment of side effects of the contamination, like fever, blockage, and windedness. Thought ought to be given to the utilization of non-prescription meds, like acetaminophen, to lessen fever and agony, as well as the organization of oxygen to patients with respiratory difficulties (Jean et al., 2020). In more severe cases, patients may require hospitalization and mechanical ventilation to breathe. To manage symptoms and avoid complications, doctors may treat secondary infections with antibiotics, corticosteroids, and anticoagulants (Stasi et al., 2020).

Notwithstanding steady consideration, a few trial drugs for the possible treatment of coronavirus are being examined. Monoclonal antibodies, which are synthetic proteins designed to target the virus and stop its replication in the body, are one of the most promising treatments (Jahanshahlu & Rezaei, 2020). Two additional treatments that are being investigated are remdesivir, an antiviral drug that has demonstrated promise in clinical trials, and convalescent plasma therapy, which uses plasma from recovered COVID-19 patients to treat those who are currently infected (Cochrane et al., 1996). It is essential to keep in mind that the effectiveness of these treatments for COVID-19 is still being evaluated and that further research is required to determine their safety and efficacy (Felsenstein et al., 2020). As a result, the coronavirus treatment strategy focuses on controlling side effects and avoiding problems, and various strong precautions and trial medications are being looked into. The COVID-19 treatment plan may change over time as the scientific community learns more about the virus (Jean et al., 2020).

Control measures and prevention strategies

SARS-CoV-2-caused coronavirus has swiftly spread around the world, causing a global pandemic. Due to the high contagiousness of the disease, it must be managed and prevented from spreading. Vaccination is one of the most efficient methods for controlling COVID-19. Vaccines have been produced and authorized for use in emergencies throughout the world, with differing degrees of success in various countries (Lotfi et al., 2020). As vaccination efforts progress, it is vital to encourage people to get all recommended immunization injections to protect themselves and other people against deadly diseases. A further tried-and-true method for preventing the spread of the virus is to use covers. It is advised to wear masks like N95, surgical, and fabric masks in various kinds of scenarios, such as offices, indoor meetings, and public transit (Karim & Karim, 2021; Santa Cruz et al., 2021). Also, social isolation is essential

for halting the infection's spread. If you stay at least 2 meters (6 feet) apart from other individuals, the virus cannot be transmitted through respiratory particles. More so, avoiding large gatherings, especially those that are inside, can aid in reducing the risk of transmission. To stop the infection from spreading, it is essential to practice proper hand hygiene. Using hand soaps that contain approximately 60% alcohol or washing your hands repeatedly for approximately 20 seconds with soap and water can stop the infection from spreading (Klein et al., 2021; Ciotti et al., 2020). It's critical to wash your hands after using public areas or touching public surfaces. To prevent the infection from spreading to others, infected persons should be isolated. Those who have been in close contact with infected individuals should also take a break to check for any negative effects and prevent further spread (Ornell et al., 2020). The most common way of finding and observing people who have had continuous contact with an infected somebody. It halts the disease from spreading by identifying potential instances early. In several countries, travelers from regions with a high transmission rate are subject to travel restrictions and quarantine to prevent the importation of cases (Ciotti et al., 2020). As a result of these actions, the infection spreads from regions with a high risk of contamination to regions with reduced transmission rates. To effectively control and prevent the spread of the coronavirus, however, a combination of these measures is required. It is essential to keep in mind that the COVID-19 condition is constantly changing, and new information and recommendations from public health authorities may necessitate modifying preventative measures (Khan et al., 2020). To aid in containing the spread of COVID-19, individuals must remain informed and adhere to the most recent public health recommendations.

Vaccination

The Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna, Johnson & Johnson, and AstraZeneca vaccinations are among the few that have been developed and approved for use against coronavirus as of April 2023. Exploiting a variety of technologies, these vaccines stimulate the immune system to identify and combat the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Adjobimey et al., 2022). The basis of the Moderna and Pfizer-BioNTech vaccines is the messenger RNA (mRNA) technology. mRNA boosters function by introducing a small quantity of genetic material from the infection into the body, which teaches cells to deliver a harmless portion of the infection known as the spike protein (Biswas et al., 2021). This surge protein then triggers an immune response that can protect against future infections. Vaccines manufactured by AstraZeneca and Johnson & Johnson utilize a viral vector technology (Crommelin et al., 2021). This technique modifies a harmless virus, not SARS-CoV-2, to transport the genetic material for SARS-CoV-2's spike protein. When a modified virus is injected into the body, the genetic material for the spike protein is delivered to cells. Then, these cells produce the spike protein and provoke an immune response (Le et al., 2020). Each of these vaccines is highly effective in preventing severe illness, hospitalization, and mortality due to COVID-19. In clinical trials, the efficacy of the vaccines from Johnson & Johnson and AstraZeneca was approximately 70-90%, whereas the

vaccines from Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna were approximately 95%. Further vaccines, including those based on protein subunits, inactivated viruses, and DNA technology, are currently in development or undertaking clinical trials (Sessa et al., 2021). Although vaccines play a crucial role in containing the COVID-19 pandemic, it is important to remember that they do not guarantee complete immunity (Hart et al., 2022). After vaccination, it is still possible to contract the virus and transmit it, but the possibility of becoming severely sick and requiring hospitalization is considerably reduced. Vaccines may not be as effective against certain virus variants, emphasizing the importance of current SARS-CoV-2 evolution research and surveillance (Tenforde et al., 2021).

Emerging Variants of the Corona Virus

There have been new coronavirus variants that have emerged since COVID-19's outbreak. Genomic sequencing has revealed these variants, which are characterized by modifications to the RNA that makes up the virus and have the prospective to alter the virus's transmissibility, severity, and ability to evade the immune system (Aleem et al., 2021). Three substantial variations have so far been distinguished: P.1 (Brazil), B.1.1.7 (UK), and B.1.351 (South Africa). These changes are believed to exhibit a higher propensity for transmission compared to the original strain of the virus, leading to increased infection rates and potentially prolonging the duration of infection (Wang et al., 2021). The B.1.1.7 variant, originating from the United Kingdom, has been detected in multiple countries and is assessed to be around 70% more transmissible than the original strain. There are indications that this variant may also be associated with an elevated risk of mortality (Singh et al., 2021). The B.1.351 variant, identified in countries including South Africa, shows signs of potential resistance to certain antibodies generated by the immune system in response to the original strain of the virus. This could potentially reduce the adequacy of COVID-19 treatments and vaccines (Lopez-Rincon et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the P.1 variant, initially discovered in Brazil but presently spreading to other countries, is believed to be more contagious than the original strain and may increase the chance of improved transmission (Lopez-Rincon et al., 2021). Monitoring the dissemination of these new variants and understanding their potential consequences for public health remains basic (Singh et al., 2021). Scientists and public health authorities are actively engaged in comprehending these variants further and devising strategies to mitigate their transmission. This includes continuing efforts to develop and distribute effective coronavirus antibodies, expanding observation of cases, and continuing genomic sequencing to identify new variants (Hoffmann et al., 2021).

Relaxing COVID-19 Restrictions: Recommencing Normalcy Despite the Emergence of New Variants

Many countries have relaxed their stringent regulations as the number of coronavirus (COVID-19) vaccinations rises and the number of cases reported decreases. Thus, significant get-togethers, travel, and the resuming of organizations are continuously getting back to pre-pandemic levels (Lai et al.,

2021). How many guidelines are released differs from one country to another, with some embracing a more careful position than others. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recently announced that fully immunized Americans can resume many activities without masks or avoid social interaction (Formeister et al., 2021). However, there are still mask regulations in place in some businesses and jurisdictions. Several European nations have reopened their borders to EU citizens and resumed allowing non-essential travel from outside the EU.

Documentation of vaccination or a negative COVID-19 test result is still required to enter certain countries (Salomon & Bilinski, 2022). While the unwinding of guidelines is a positive turn of events, it is fundamental to consider that the pandemic isn't yet over and that new infections keep on arising (Chenchula et al., 2022). As a result, adhering to public health guidelines like washing one's hands frequently, wearing a face mask, and isolating oneself when necessary is essential. The World Health Association (WHO) keeps on giving direction on the pandemic, accentuating the significance of checking what is going on and staying watchful (Wong et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

This study reveals that the SARS-CoV-2 virus's COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant global impact. High rates of morbidity and mortality have resulted from the virus's rapid global spread. The sickness can show clinically in various structures, going from asymptomatic cases to perilous ailments. The risk of severe illness and death from the virus is increased by age, obesity, ethnicity, occupation, living conditions, travel history, social behaviors, and preexisting medical conditions. PCR, serology, and radiology have been conceived as symptomatic apparatuses to support the conclusion of Coronavirus. Supportive care, immunomodulators, and antivirals are some of the COVID-19 treatment options. Nevertheless, more effective treatments are still needed. Vaccination efforts are ongoing and emergency vaccines have been developed and approved for use worldwide. Putting on a mask, avoiding social contact, practicing proper hand hygiene, quarantine, isolation, contact tracing, and travel restrictions have been implemented to control and prevent the virus's spread. The prevention strategies may need to be altered as a result of new information and advice from public health authorities

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Each study has limitations; thus, you can describe it here and briefly provide suggestions for further research.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This section gives you the opportunity to thank your colleagues who provided suggestions for your paper. You can also express your appreciation for the financial assistance you received, in completing this research.

REFERENCES

- Adjobimey, T., Meyer, J., Sollberg, L., Bawolt, M., Berens, C., Kovačević, P., & Hoerauf, A. (2022). Comparison of IgA, IgG, and neutralizing antibody responses following immunization with Moderna, BioNTech, AstraZeneca, Sputnik-V.
- Johnson and Johnson, and Sinopharm's COVID-19 vaccines. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 13, 3094.
- Aleem, A., AB, A. S., & Slenker, A. K. (2021). Emerging variants of SARS-CoV-2 and novel therapeutics against coronavirus (COVID-19).
- Ao, Z., Jing Ouyang, M., Olukitibi, T. A., Warner, B., Vendramelli, R., Truong, T., & Yao, X. (2021). Development and Characterization of Recombinant Vesicular Stomatitis Virus (rVSV)-based Bivalent Vaccine Against COVID-19 Delta Variant and Influenza Virus. *bioRxiv*, 2021-12.
- Araf, Y., Akter, F., Tang, Y. D., Fatemi, R., Parvez, M. S. A., Zheng, C., & Hossain, M. G. (2022). Omicron variant of SARS-CoV-2: genomics, transmissibility, and responses to current COVID-19 vaccines. *Journal of medicaMedical Virology*, 1825-1832.
- Archer, S. L., Sharp, W. W., & Weir, E. K. (2020). Differentiating COVID-19 pneumonia from acute respiratory distress syndrome and high altitude pulmonary edema: therapeutic implications. *Circulation*, 142(2), 101-104.
- Asselah, T., Durantel, D., Pasmant, E., Lau, G., & Schinazi, R. F. (2021). COVID-19: Discovery, diagnostics and drug development. *Journal of Hepatology*, 74(1), 168-184.
- Baud, D., Qi, X., Nielsen-Saines, K., Musso, D., Pomar, L., & Favre, G. (2020). Real estimates of mortality following COVID-19 infection. *The Lancet infectInfectious Diseases*, 773.
- Biswas, N., Mustapha, T., Khubchandani, J., & Price, J. H. (2021). The nature and extent of COVID-19 vaccination hesitancy in healthcare workers. *Journal of Community Health*1244-1251.
- Bourgonje, A. R., Abdulle, A. E., Timens, W., Hillebrands, J. L., Navis, G. J., Gordijn, S. J., ... & van Goor, H. (2020). Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), SARS-CoV-2 and the pathophysiology of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *The Journal of Pathology*, 251(3), 228-248.
- Chenchula, S., Karunakaran, P., Sharma, S., & Chavan, M. (2022). Current evidence on the efficacy of COVID-19 booster dose vaccination against the

- Omicron variant: A systematic review. *Journal of Medical Virology*, 94(7), 2969-2976.
- Cherian, S., Potdar, V., Jadhav, S., Yadav, P., Gupta, N., Das, M., & Team, N. I. C. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 spike mutations, L452R, T478K, E484Q, and P681R, in the second wave of COVID-19 in Maharashtra, India. *Microorganisms*, 9(7), 1542.
- Ciotti, M., Ciccozzi, M., Terrinoni, A., Jiang, W. C., Wang, C. B., & Bernardini, S. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic. *Critical reviews in clinical laboratory sciences*, 57(6), 365-388.
- Cochrane Haematology Group, Ansems, K., Grundeis, F., Dahms, K., Mikolajewska, A., Thieme, V., & Fichtner, F. (1996). Remdesivir for the treatment of COVID-19. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 2021(8).
- Crommelin, D. J., Volkin, D. B., Hoogendoorn, K. H., Lubiniecki, A. S., & Jiskoot, W. (2021). The science is there: key considerations for stabilizing viral vector-based Covid-19 vaccines. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 110(2), 627-634.
- Dambha-Miller, H., Hinton, W., Wilcox, C. R., Lemanska, A., Joy, M., Feher, M., & Griffin, S. (2023). Mortality from angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers in people infected with COVID-19: a cohort study of 3.7 million people. *Family practice*, 40(2), 330-337.
- De Almeida-Pititto, B., Dualib, P. M., Zajdenverg, L., Dantas, J. R., De Souza, F. D., Rodacki, M., & Brazilian Diabetes Society Study Group (SBD). (2020). Severity and mortality of COVID-19 in patients with diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease: a meta-analysis. *Diabetology & metabolic syndrome*, 12, 1-12.
- Felsenstein, S., Herbert, J. A., McNamara, P. S., & Hedrich, C. M. (2020). COVID-19: Immunology and treatment options. *Clinical immunology*, 215, 108448.
- Fernández, A. (2021). Molecular biology clues portray SARS-CoV-2 as a gain-of-function laboratory manipulation of bat CoV RaTG13. *ACS Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 12(6), 941-942.
- Formeister, E. J., Chien, W., Agrawal, Y., Carey, J. P., Stewart, C. M., & Sun, D. Q. (2021). Preliminary analysis of the association between COVID-19 vaccination and sudden hearing loss using US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention vaccine adverse events reporting system data. *JAMA Otolaryngology-Head & Neck Surgery*, 147(7), 674-676.

- Giannis, D., Ziogas, I. A., & Gianni, P. (2020). Coagulation disorders in coronavirus infected patients: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-1, MERS-CoV and lessons from the past. *Journal of Clinical Virology*, 127, 104362.
- Gordon, D. E., Jang, G. M., Bouhaddou, M., Xu, J., Obernier, K., White, K. M., & Krogan, N. J. (2020). A SARS-CoV-2 protein interaction map reveals targets for drug repurposing. *Nature*, 583(7816), 459-468.
- Goudouris, E. S. (2021). Laboratory diagnosis of COVID-19. *Jornal de pediatria*, 97, 7-12.
- Güner, H. R., Hasanoğlu, İ., & Aktaş, F. (2020). COVID-19: Prevention and control measures in the community. *Turkish Journal of medical Sciences*, 571-577.
- Guo, Y. R., Cao, Q. D., Hong, Z. S., Tan, Y. Y., Chen, S. D., Jin, H. J., & Yan, Y. (2020). The origin, transmission and clinical therapies on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak—an update on the status. *Military medical research*, 7, 1-10.
- Hart, J. D., Chokephaibulkit, K., Mayxay, M., Ong-Lim, A. L. T., Saketa, S. T., & Russell, F. M. (2022). COVID-19 vaccine boosters in the Asia-Pacific region in the context of Omicron. *The Lancet Regional Health—Western Pacific*, 20.
- Hashim, M. J., Alsuwaidi, A. R., & Khan, G. (2020). Population risk factors for COVID-19 mortality in 93 countries. *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health*, 204.
- Hernández-Huerta, M. T., Mayoral, L. P. C., Navarro, L. M. S., Mayoral-Andrade, G., Mayoral, E. P. C., Zenteno, E., & Pérez-Campos, E. (2021). Should RT-PCR be considered a gold standard in the diagnosis of COVID-19? *Journal of Medical Virology*, 93(1), 137.
- Hoffmann, M., Arora, P., Groß, R., Seidel, A., Hörnich, B. F., Hahn, A. S., & Pöhlmann, S. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 variants B. 1.351 and P. 1 escape from neutralizing antibodies. *Cell*, 184(9), 2384-2393.
- Hu, B., Guo, H., Zhou, P., & Shi, Z. L. (2021). Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 19(3), 141-154.
- Hutchins, H. J., Wolff, B., Leeb, R., Ko, J. Y., Odom, E., Willey, J., & Bitsko, R. H. (2020). COVID-19 mitigation behaviors by age group—United States, April–June 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 69(43), 1584.
- Jahanshahlu, L., & Rezaei, N. (2020). A monoclonal antibody as a potential anti-COVID-19. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 129, 110337.
- Jean, S. S., Lee, P. I., & Hsueh, P. R. (2020). Treatment options for COVID-19: The reality and challenges. *Journal of Microbiology, immunology, and Infection*, 53(3), 436-443.

- Jones, I., & Roy, P. (2021). The Sputnik V COVID-19 vaccine candidate appears safe and effective. *The Lancet*, 397(10275), 642-643.
- Jungreis, I., Sealfon, R., & Kellis, M. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 gene content and COVID-19 mutation impact by comparing 44 Sarbecovirus genomes. *Nature communications*, 12(1), 2642.
- Karim, S. S. A., & Karim, Q. A. (2021). Omicron SARS-CoV-2 variant: a new chapter in the COVID-19 pandemic. *The Lancet*, 398(10317), 2126-2128.
- Khan, A. U., Proma, A. A., Akter, M., Rahaman, M. M., & Das, S. (2020). A review of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) epidemic threat for global health in 2020. *American Journal of Microbiological Research*, 8(2), 57-62.
- Khoury, J., Najjar-Debbiny, R., Hanna, A., Jabbour, A., Ahmad, Y. A., Saffuri, A., & Hakim, F. (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-Long-term immune decline and breakthrough infections. *Vaccine*, 39(48), 6984-6989.
- Klein, H., Asseo, K., Karni, N., Benjamini, Y., Nir-Paz, R., Muszkat, M., & Niv, M. Y. (2021). Onset, duration, and unresolved symptoms, including smell and taste changes, in mild COVID-19 infection: a cohort study in Israeli patients. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 27(5), 769-774.
- Ko, J. Y., DeSisto, C. L., Simeone, R. M., Ellington, S., Galang, R. R., Oduyebo, T., & Shapiro-Mendoza, C. K. (2021). Adverse pregnancy outcomes, maternal complications, and severe illness among US delivery hospitalizations with and without a coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) diagnosis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 73(Supplement_1), S24-S31.
- Konatham, T. K., Satyanarayana Reddy, K., Masipogu, A., & Vallakeerthi, N. (2020). A Review of viruses that originated from China; SARS, MERS, and COVID-19. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 9(5), 2010-2015.
- Lai, D., Cai, Y., Chan, T. H., Gan, D., Hurson, A. N., & Zhang, Y. D. (2022). How to organize travel restrictions in the new future: lessons from the COVID-19 response in Hong Kong and Singapore. *BMJ Global Health*, 7(2), e006975.
- Le, T. T., Andreadakis, Z., Kumar, A., Román, R. G., Tollefsen, S., Saville, M., & Mayhew, S. (2020). The COVID-19 vaccine development landscape. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*, 19(5), 305-306.
- Lopez-Rincon, A., Perez-Romero, C. A., Tonda, A., Mendoza-Maldonado, L., Claassen, E., Garssen, J., & Kraneveld, A. D. (2021). Design of specific primer sets for the detection of B. 1.1. 7, B. 1.351 and P. 1 SARS-CoV-2 variants using deep learning. *BioRxiv*, 70.

- Lotfi, M., Hamblin, M. R., & Rezaei, N. (2020). COVID-19: Transmission, prevention, and potential therapeutic opportunities. *Clinica chimica acta*, 508, 254-266.
- Lu, Q., Zhu, Z., Tan, C., Zhou, H., Hu, Y., Shen, G., & Xie, X. (2021). Changes of serum IL-10, IL-1 β , IL-6, MCP-1, TNF- α , IP-10 and IL-4 in COVID-19 patients. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 75(9), e14462.
- Mehraeen, E., Salehi, M. A., Behnezhad, F., Moghaddam, H. R., & SeyedAlinaghi, S. (2021). Transmission modes of COVID-19: a systematic review. *Infectious Disorders-Drug Targets (Formerly Current Drug Targets-Infectious Disorders)*, 21(6), 27-34.
- Nabi, K. N. (2020). Forecasting COVID-19 pandemic: A data-driven analysis. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 139, 110046.
- Ng, M. Y., Lee, E. Y., Yang, J., Yang, F., Li, X., Wang, H., & Kuo, M. D. (2020). Imaging profile of the COVID-19 infection: radiologic findings and literature review. *Radiology: Cardiothoracic Imaging*, 2(1), e200034.
- Ornell, F., Moura, H. F., Scherer, J. N., Pechansky, F., Kessler, F. H. P., & von Diemen, L. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on substance use: Implications for prevention and treatment. *Psychiatry Research*, 289, 113096.
- Ouassou, H., Kharchoufa, L., Bouhrim, M., Daoudi, N. E., Imtara, H., Bencheikh, N., & Bnouham, M. (2020). The Pathogenesis of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): evaluation and prevention. *Journal of Immunology Research*, 2020.
- Paterson, R. W., Brown, R. L., Benjamin, L., Nortley, R., Wiethoff, S., Bharucha, T., & Zandi, M. S. (2020). The emerging spectrum of COVID-19 neurology: clinical, radiological and laboratory findings. *Brain*, 143(10), 3104-3120.
- Qiu, J., Shen, B., Zhao, M., Wang, Z., Xie, B., & Xu, Y. (2020). A nationwide survey of psychological distress among Chinese people in the COVID-19 epidemic: implications and policy recommendations. *General psychiatry*, 33(2).
- Raza, S., Navid, M. T., Zahir, W., Khan, M. N., Awais, M., Yaqub, T., & Rasheed, M. A. (2021). Analysis of the spike proteins suggests pangolin is an intermediate host of COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2). *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 25(3).
- Rokni, M., Hamblin, M. R., & Rezaei, N. (2020). Cytokines and COVID-19: Friends or Foes? *Human vaccines & immunotherapeutics*, 16(10), 2363-2365.

- Rothan, H. A., & Byrareddy, S. N. (2020). The epidemiology and pathogenesis of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak. *Journal of autoimmunity*, 109, 102433.
- Salian, V. S., Wright, J. A., Vedell, P. T., Nair, S., Li, C., Kandimalla, M., & Kandimalla, K. K. (2021). COVID-19 transmission, current treatment, and future therapeutic strategies. *Molecular pharmaceutics*, 18(3), 754-771.
- Salomon, J. A., & Bilinski, A. (2022). Evaluating the performance of Centers for Disease Control and Prevention COVID-19 community levels as leading indicators of COVID-19 mortality. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 175(9), 1240-1249.
- Santa Cruz, A., Mendes-Frias, A., Oliveira, A. I., Dias, L., Matos, A. R., Carvalho, A., & Silvestre, R. (2021). Interleukin-6 is a biomarker for the development of fatal severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 pneumonia. *Frontiers in immunology*, 12, 613422.
- Sayampanathan, A. A., Heng, C. S., Pin, P. H., Pang, J., Leong, T. Y., & Lee, V. J. (2021). Infectivity of asymptomatic versus symptomatic COVID-19. *The Lancet*, 397(10269), 93-94.
- Schlick, T., Zhu, Q., Jain, S., & Yan, S. (2021). Structure-altering mutations of the SARS-CoV-2 frameshifting RNA element. *Biophysical journal*, 120(6), 1040-1053.
- Sessa, M., Kragholm, K., Hviid, A., & Andersen, M. (2021). Thromboembolic events in younger women exposed to Pfizer-BioNTech or Moderna COVID-19 vaccines. *Expert opinion on drug safety*, 20(11), 1451-1453.
- Singh, J., Samal, J., Kumar, V., Sharma, J., Agrawal, U., Ehtesham, N. Z., & Hasnain, S. E. (2021). Structure-function analyses of new SARS-CoV-2 variants B. 1.1. 7, B. 1.351, and B. 1.1. 28.1: clinical, diagnostic, therapeutic, and public health implications. *Viruses*, 13(3), 439.
- Singhal, T. (2020). A review of coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19). *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 87(4), 281-286.
- Stasi, C., Fallani, S., Voller, F., & Silvestri, C. (2020). Treatment for COVID-19: An overview. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, 889, 173644.
- Sultan, L. R., & Sehgal, C. M. (2020). A review of early experience in lung ultrasound in diagnosing and managing COVID-19. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*, 46(9), 2530-2545.

- Tenforde, M. W., Self, W. H., Naioti, E. A., Ginde, A. A., Douin, D. J., Olson, S. M., & Cass, C. (2021). Sustained effectiveness of Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna vaccines against COVID-19 associated hospitalizations among adults – United States, March–July 2021. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 70(34), 1156.
- Udomsinprasert, W., Jittikoon, J., Sangroongruangsri, S., & Chaikledkaew, U. (2021). Circulating levels of interleukin-6 and interleukin-10, but not tumor necrosis factor-alpha, as potential biomarkers of severity and mortality for COVID-19: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Journal of Clinical Immunology*, 41, 11-22.
- Verity, R., Okell, L. C., Dorigatti, I., Winskill, P., Whittaker, C., Imai, N., & Ferguson, N. M. (2020). Estimates of the severity of COVID-19 disease. *MedRxiv*, 2020-03.
- Wang, L., He, W. B., Yu, X. M., Hu, D. L., & Jiang, H. (2020). Prolonged prothrombin time at admission predicts poor clinical outcomes in COVID-19 patients. *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, 8(19), 4370.
- Wang, P., Nair, M. S., Liu, L., Iketani, S., Luo, Y., Guo, Y., & Ho, D. D. (2021). Antibody resistance of SARS-CoV-2 variants B. 1.351 and B. 1.1. 7. *Nature*, 593(7857), 130-135.
- Wong, M. K., Brooks, D. J., Ikejezie, J., Gacic-Dobo, M., Dumolard, L., Nedelec, Y., & Van Kerkhove, M. D. (2023). COVID-19 mortality and Progress toward vaccinating older adults – World Health Organization, worldwide, 2020–2022. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 72(5), 113.
- Xu, K., Cai, H., Shen, Y., Ni, Q., Chen, Y., Hu, S., & Li, L. (2020). Management of COVID-19: The Zhejiang experience. *Zhejiang da xue xue bao. Yi xue ban= Journal of Zhejiang University. Medical sciences*, 49(2), 147-157.
- Yager, E. J. (2020). Antibody-dependent enhancement and COVID-19: moving toward acquittal. *Clinical Immunology (Orlando, Fla.)*, 217, 108496.
- Yang, L., Liu, S., Liu, J., Zhang, Z., Wan, X., Huang, B., & Zhang, Y. (2020). COVID-19: immunopathogenesis and Immunotherapeutics. *Signal transduction and targeted therapy*, 5(1), 128.
- Zhao, X., Liu, S., Yin, Y., Zhang, T., & Chen, Q. (2022). Airborne transmission of COVID-19 virus in enclosed spaces: an overview of research methods. *Indoor air*, 32(6), e13056.